

Photometric and Positional Accuracy of Star Mapper

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Some preliminary results are given of a study of quasi-real time processing of a continuous stream of Star Mapper data. The aim is to estimate the detection power of such processing, i.e. how faint stars can be detected with a delay of only a few seconds.

To avoid discussion of transmission curves etc, the results are given in terms of two parameters b and a , which are related to the background count rate and the stellar brightness as follows:

b = average number of counts per sample (=1/600 sec) when there is no star on either slit system;

a = average number of counts per sample that would result from a given star if the grid were replaced by a clear plate (i.e., corresponding to $\delta = 1$).

Typical values may be $a = 1$ for a $B = 12$ star, and $b = 2$. The results are rather insensitive to spectral response and colour; however, the numbers given refer to $B-V = 0.75$ and the response of the MATRA instrument (Dec. 1979). Slightly better performance (for the same a and b) can be expected with restricted wavelength bands.

Results are given for the vertical slit system ($\theta = 0$) and inclined ($\theta = 45^\circ$).

Photometric accuracy:

$$\sigma_m = 1.086 (1/a) (0.11a + 0.31b)^{\frac{1}{2}} \quad [\text{mag}] \quad (\theta = 0)$$

$$\sigma_m = 1.086 (1/a) (0.10a + 0.45b)^{\frac{1}{2}} \quad [\text{mag}] \quad (\theta = 45^\circ)$$

Positional accuracy:

$$\sigma_\eta = (1/a) (0.016a + 0.062b)^{\frac{1}{2}} \quad [\text{arcsec}] \quad (\theta = 0)$$

$$\sigma_\eta = (1/a) (0.044a + 0.22b)^{\frac{1}{2}} \quad [\text{arcsec}] \quad (\theta = 45^\circ)$$

Detection power:

The probability that a given star is detected from a single transit across one of the slit systems depends on the detection threshold applied by the detection algorithm. The probability can be increased by setting the threshold to a low value, but then the number of false (spurious) detections increases too. Define

F = frequency of false detections (per second per slit system);

$a_{\frac{1}{2}}$ = stellar count rate at which the probability of detection is $\frac{1}{2}$ (probability > 0.5 for $a > a_{\frac{1}{2}}$).

The following table gives $a_{\frac{1}{2}}$ for each slit system, as a function of F .

The table has been computed for $b = 2$, but the detectability depends mainly on the ratio a^2/b , so that a table for $b = 4$ (say) can be obtained by multiplying the values $a_{\frac{1}{2}}$ by a factor $\sqrt{2}$.

F (Hz)	$a_{\frac{1}{2}}$ ($\theta = 0$)	$a_{\frac{1}{2}}$ ($\theta = 45^\circ$)
0.1	3.1	3.7
0.2	2.9	3.4
0.5	2.7	3.1
1.0	2.4	2.9
2.0	2.2	2.6
5.0	1.9	2.2